

Closed-Loop Automation in 6G for Minimum Downtime Task Continuity in Surveillance Cobots

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Abstract—This research delves deeply into the integration of collaborative robots (cobots) in the context of advancing 6G technology, aiming to enhance situational awareness. The research underscores the critical importance of Closed-Loop (CL) cobot control within the evolving 6G network architecture, enabling increased automation and improved adaptability. The study provides a comprehensive background on Intent-Based Networks (IBN) and CL mechanisms, introduces an application scenario, and outlines a framework for implementing CL systems in cobot cluster networks. An experimental setup is detailed, and a CL-enabled application migration use-case is demonstrated. This work contributes valuable insights to the ongoing discussion on the evolution of next-generation networks.

Index Terms—6G, cobots, Intent-Based Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly advancing landscape of communication, sensing, and automation technologies, the pursuit of heightened situational awareness takes centre stage, aiming to enhance these systems' capacity to understand and adapt to diverse scenarios [1]. Consequently, initial research into the sixth generation (6G) aims to build situational awareness in telecommunications networks by enabling information flow between the application and network domains. With an understanding of live application services, 6G networks will be able to provide the best network experience tailored to each application [2].

To achieve automated network management, the ETSI Zero-Touch Service Management (ZSM) Industry Specification Group (ZSM ISG) has developed a standard for ZSM networks [3]. ZSM aims to automate the life cycle of network and application services without human intervention in setup or operation [4]. This is done through the declaration of intents, which express the desired state of a platform. A set of parameters and system actors relevant to the intent are used to configure Closed-Loop (CL) control systems. CL mechanisms are the underlying controllers that autonomously manage the observation, analysis, decision-making, and actuation stages for each service component [5].

The development of CL control within the ZSM paradigm has garnered significant attention across academia and industry. Recent academic investigations focus on strategies and methodologies for enhancing CL coordination. Using the established ZSM ISG standards, the development of frameworks for the synchronized and efficient initiation and operation of

multiple CL mechanisms [6]. Furthermore, independent explorations have delved into autonomous management frameworks. Such as employing multi-agent reinforcement learning agents to enforce specified Key Performance Indicators (KPI) [7]. However, few studies have yet to examine the performance of CL systems in real-world application services.

One application service that has garnered significant attention in the mobile network research community is the deployment of collaborative robots (cobots). Cobots are robots that operate dynamically in shared human environments to provide adaptable, efficient solutions across multiple domains [8]. To ensure robust communication networks for collaborative robots, researchers have identified the *robots to cobots* use case category for defining the requirements of 6G networks [9].

This research explores a novel implementation of CL control system on a cobot service. A novel implementation of the ZSM framework is introduced to enhance situational awareness and collaboration, while also minimizing downtime in the cobot tasks. Provided is also a comprehensive description of a testbed with 5G connectivity, on which a CL system is implemented. Additionally, an application migration experiment is performed between two cobots without noticeable interruptions in the service.

The remainder sections of this paper are structured as follows: Section II provides a comprehensive background review of Intent Based Networks (IBN) and CL control principles. In Section III, an application scenario is presented, along with the introduction of a framework for implementing CL mechanisms in cobot networks. Section IV outlines the experimental setup of our testbed. Section V reports results on the experimental platform. Lastly, Section VI summarizes the key contributions and discusses future work.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Intent-Based Networks and Closed-Loop Control

In the context of network automation and service management, a crucial aspect involves examining and assessing intent-based management. A comprehensive study has been conducted to identify the essential elements required for designing an end-to-end solution for IBN. This solution aims to autonomously manage services across various administrative

Fig. 1: CL system interaction with the testbed

domains as efficiently as possible by utilizing intent-based requests [10].

A management entity based on intents, is a system that employs either natural language intents or a predetermined syntax on standardized interfaces to express desired behaviors or outcomes for a network or system, without specifying particular implementations [11]. In the context of telecommunications (telco) networks, intents play a crucial role in simplifying service and network resource management by interpreting requests expressed in simple human language, for instance, "Deploy service C between endpoints A and B." The system then executes these intents through various enablers. This work specifically concentrates on the CL enabler and explores its integration in a cobot use case within a single management domain [4].

The usage of CL control as a means to realize network automation is a research topic widely investigated over the years. With the emergence of 6G, the necessity for automating network operations became inherent. The aim of this tight integration is to reduce the need for human oversight and control in increasingly complex systems, thus minimizing both the frequency and duration of intervention as well as lowering operational expenses. A CL system is always characterized by 3 or 4 steps (or stages) that allow i) the continuous monitoring of the target system ii) the analysis of the collected data, iii) a decision on the analyzed data, and iv) the enforcement of the corrective actions on the target system. While the composition of CL systems has not changed meaningfully, its implementation has evolved [4].

B. Closed-Loop Components

The high degree of automation characterizing the 6G systems spans the whole network continuum (core, edge, extreme edge) at different levels of abstraction (physical infrastructure, network applications, etc.), generating the coexistence of multiple CL systems insisting on the same resources. In order to avoid enforcement of inconsistent configurations, ETSI ZSM introduced in [4] the concept of CL governance and coordination. A CL Governance (CLG) entity is responsible for the loop management and exposes functionalities to allow external users to interact with the loop (goal configuration, start/stop, retrieve status, etc.). A CL Coordination (CLC) system is a set of functionalities that allow to mitigate or even avoid conflicts between concurrent CL functions.

In [12], a CL system consists on a set of components.

- The Resource Orchestrator (RO) is responsible for the dynamic discovery, continuous monitoring and inventory of heterogeneous virtualization platforms and devices of the Extreme-Edge, Edge and Cloud Continuum. Additionally, it enables service application orchestration.
- CL Governance (CLG) is a service responsible for the life-cycle management of CL functions. Upon the definition of CL functions (i.e., monitoring, analysis, decision, and execution) through dedicated blueprints, the deployment of the latter is executed through the RO, that takes care of instantiating each CL function.
- Service Orchestrator (SO) is the component responsible for the high-level lifecycle management of service applications coordinating the RO and the CLG modules. Upon the definition of a service application with its associated

CL system through Vertical Service Blueprints (VSBs) and Vertical Service Descriptors (VSDs), SO takes care to request the deployment of the application through the RO and the deployment of the CL functions through CLG.

III. SCENARIO

In this work, we illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed closed loop automation applied to a cobot task continuity use-case. The scenario consists of a set of cobots performing a surveillance task in industrial premises. This task involves video streaming from the cobots to a remote server for video decomposition, thus offloading computation from the cobot. In instances when the cobot's battery depletes, an auxiliary cobot is deployed, seamlessly assuming and continuing the tasks from its predecessor. This process is facilitated by the CL approach, which aims to minimize downtime during robot exchanges. The CL system triggers a transfer of resources and the context without hindering the service performance for the intent consumer.

In Figure 1, the scenario is described. On the left hand side we have the CL entities, i.e SO, RO, CLG service. On the right-hand side we have the cluster resources in which the surveillance task is performed, servers running video decomposition algorithms robots surveilling the premises and reporting metrics. In order to fulfill the intent, that is, minimize the downtime of the task by anticipating the replacement of the task workers (cobots) the CL entities perform the following tasks [12].

The SO requests through the RO to deploy the necessary applications on the current task worker (cobot). These applications enable the surveillance task such as the RTSP pipeline to send a stream to the video decomposition server, an MQTT publisher application to report the battery consumption of the cobot and a network monitoring application to provide QoS analytics, among others.

Additionally the SO requests the CLG to provision CL functions. The CL functions implement a feedback loop. In Figure 1 these functions are, cl-monitoring, cl-analytics, cl-decision and cl-execution.

The cl-monitoring function, collects data required for the system automation from the system itself. In our scenario, the battery metrics determine whether a cobot is able to perform a task, additionally the resource consumption is collected. The cl-analysis analyses the data collected to derive information on what is happening on the monitored devices. For instance, if the cobot is exceedingly expending CPU resources, it would advance battery depletion. The cl-decision function, takes the insights provided by the analytics service to make corrective decisions. This could be to establish a new battery threshold to replace a task worker, based on the current task worker's resource consumption. The cl-execution, is the final stage of the CL workflow, in charge of enforcing the decisions made by the CL functions. This is, the cl-execution function requests the RO to migrate applications and provide the necessary context to the next task worker, so it can continue where its

predecessor left off. Once a cobot finalizes its task it returns to the charging station to prepare to repeat the cycle.

The adoption of AI/ML models for the analysis and decision stages allows us to go beyond the classical reactive actions, enabling the CL functions to perform predictive adjustments to the target system. For instance instead of having a constant battery threshold to trigger the cobot replacement, an AI-based CL system can predict the future level of the battery (based on resource consumption) to make informed decisions. With this, the system can decide to offload the cobot's task to an edge server or another cobot, preserving the battery duration. Alternatively, the CL functions may decide to charge the battery, although not at a critical level, exploiting the best charging time windows for sustainable energy consumption.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this section, we present a testbed setup showcasing a series of technologies and solutions. The goal is to describe a system that has the potential for enabling a higher levels of service and network automation.

A. Testbed Hardware Components

Fig. 2: Cobot used in the experimental tests

The hardware components of the testbed are the following:

- A 5G Stand Alone (SA) Network composed of Nokia ASiR RAN elements and a Open5GS core.
- Two cobots operated with Raspberry Pi 4. They use a Telewell modem with 5G SA support. Additionally, each cobot has a set of sensors and a motor with wheels.
- Three Debian Servers , each 8 CPUs and 32 GB RAM. One of which, equipped with a GPU.
- A PC where the CL three macro-components of the orchestration stack are deployed, within a Virtual Machine (Debian OS, 4 vCPU, 8GB RAM).

Lead-acid batteries provide power to the Raspberry Pi through a regulator, but beforehand a voltmeter sensor is installed. The battery level's decay is measured from its voltage output.

Fig. 3: Diagram of application Kubernetes architecture

B. Kubernetes Cluster Setup

For the application scenario, this paper proposes a Kubernetes-based edge architecture, designed to enable a fluid transition between robots responsible for distinct tasks.

In Figure 3, we provide an overview of the testbed's configuration as from the Kubernetes platform's perspective. Our chosen setup utilizes the K3s distribution of Kubernetes, known for its lightweight and simplified nature, making it particularly suitable for environments with limited resources. The K3s cluster is composed of six nodes. In Kubernetes, nodes refer to computing devices where Kubernetes workloads are deployed. These nodes are further categorized into master and worker nodes.

Within the cluster, the master node houses the control plane, responsible for managing Kubernetes API requests and orchestrating and scheduling workloads in the cluster. The worker nodes execute the workloads. We categorize worker nodes into two types: edge-cloud nodes and cobot nodes. The former nodes running on our servers have abundant resources, with both ample power supply and computational capacity, while the latter, running on the cobots local computers have limited computation and battery capacity. The workloads consist on series of dockerized applications, pods.

In this application scenario, see Figure 3, we have deployed 5 pods to run the workloads:

- 1) The CL Functions Pod is responsible for running the cl-analysis, cl-decision and cl-execution functions.
- 2) The Object Detection Pod runs an instance of Yolo v6. It collects the live video stream from the cobot, performs object detection, and provides the ROS Master node with a report of the video analysis.

- 3) The ROS Master Pod is responsible for running the ROS Master node workload, which ensures seamless communication and coordination among the ROS pods.
- 4) The ROS Pod is responsible for running the ROS worker node workloads on the cobot's local machine. These nodes handle multiple tasks including hardware control, motion planning, and image and battery data collection.
- 5) The MQTT Pod runs an MQTT broker responsible for distributing information within the cluster.

In order to optimize the allocation of workloads according to resource availability, we employ Kubernetes taints and tolerations in our configuration. This strategy enables us to carefully assign specific workloads to nodes with the suitable resources, ensuring the efficient utilization of the existing infrastructure. While cobot nodes focus on collecting sensor data, network metrics, and hardware operation, the edge computing nodes are equipped to handle workloads that involve data analysis, orchestration, and Machine Learning.

V. RESULTS

Once the testbed has been presented, we proceed to showcase an application migration use case. First, the application, a network monitoring application, is introduced and a series of experimental results are presented. Afterwards, the migration of the aforementioned application is performed using a CL system. Illustrating the seamless assumption of a workload by the replacement cobot.

A. Network Monitoring Application and Tests

In order for the cobot to perform a surveillance task, network connectivity must be available and have a capable performance. Moreover, for the task migration use case to be successful, network resources between the server nodes and the cobots are monitored. This ensures a seamless transition of the applications needed for surveillance. The connectivity provided by the 5G SA network ensures that the integrity of the CL system and the Kubernetes cluster is preserved.

The 3GPP, has identified throughput and latency as KPI metrics for mobile networks. In this work, we develop a network monitoring application which allows real-time evaluation of the cobots connectivity in the RAN. The application uses network tools, ping and iperf3, to collect Round Trip Time (RTT) and throughput metrics, respectively.

In Figure 4, the monitoring pipeline is described. The network monitoring application performs measurements between two endpoints the cobots and the edge-cloud servers. Note, that in a edge-cloud server, an iperf3 server is deployed to establish the connection with the application client. Once the connection is established, the network KPI metrics are generated at the network monitoring application (client), in the cobot. Over the 5G SA RAN, the application publishes the metrics in JSON format to a MQTT Broker on the edge-cloud server. Afterwards, the a Telegraf, InfluxDB and Grafana stack (TIG stack), subscribes to the MQTT Broker, stores the metrics and displays them in a dashboard, respectively.

Fig. 4: Simplified measurement setup. Measurement actors and the software stack are shown.

These tools may be applied to any testbeds with similar characteristics. Some preliminary tests were performed in ours to evaluate its' capabilities towards fulfilling the use-case scenario. The tests consisted on driving the cobot, in a loop inside a lab room during 5 minutes. The results are presented below. The ping measurements, Figure 5, obtained

Fig. 5: Time series plot of the RTT test (ms)

300 samples, and yielded the following results. The median of the measurement is 10.1 ms and the standard deviation 2.36. Fluctuations are present but not significant, the mean value is 10.49 ms and the maximum is 17 ms. Overall the round trip time values are stable and the system is able to host low latency applications. The TCP iperf3 uplink measurement, Figure 6, obtained 300 samples, and yielded the following results. The median value of the measurement is 54.70 Mbps and the standard deviation 4.50. The figure shows noticeable fluctuations in the throughput measurement. Nevertheless, the results show that the platform is capable of transmitting

Fig. 6: Time series plot of the throughput test (Mbps)

video streams with sufficient frame rate and resolution for the surveillance mission use case.

Additionally, the same network KPI measurements were performed while a cobot remained in a fixed position with direct line of site to the indoor base station. The uplink throughput yielded significantly better results. 64.5 Mbps median value with less fluctuation, and a standard deviation of 1.76 were obtained. Obstacles blocking the line of sight (i.e. chairs, tables ...) may cause the results previously presented.

Overall, these tests show a containerized network monitoring platform in action. This allows for flexible management and scalable use of the monitoring tools. The numeric results have shown that this testbed is suitable to perform the tasks expected from the scenario presented in Section III.

B. Use Case Application Migration

In this section, the application presented in Section V.A is used to demonstrate the CL workflow.

The SO initiates the application deployment on the task worker (cobot) through the RO, along with a dedicated battery threshold based CL function. This monitors the battery levels of both the task worker and the replacement cobots by subscribing to the corresponding MQTT topics. Additionally, though the CLG, cl-analysis, cl-decision and cl-execution functions are deployed. The cl-analysis processes the metrics collected from cl-monitoring, and the cl-decision and cl-execution triggers the application migration to the replacement cobot when needed.

The application migration use case is presented in a Kubernetes Dashboard, a human friendly user interface to view the microservices deployed in a cluster. In this test, the migration is triggered artificially. This is, battery metrics below the determined threshold are published so the cl-decision requests the migration to the RO. The threshold is fixed considering the battery voltage range supported for normal cobot operation, as detailed in Section IV.

In Figure 7, the initial state of the cluster applications is displayed in the Kubernetes Dashboard. The target application shown in the Name column, client-app, is deployed in robo-pi1 (Node column). This is the name given to the first task worker node. Additionally, applications robo1 and hexa-x-ii-broker-mosquitto are shown. The former is the ROS worker

Fig. 7: Cobot application deployed in robo-pi1

Fig. 8: Cobot application migrated in robo-pi2

application in charge of operating the robot's sensors and motors, and the later, the MQTT Broker where all metrics are published.

In Figure 8, the final state of the use-case is shown. Artificially, battery metrics under the threshold, are published to the MQTT Broker and subsequently fed into the CL pipeline. The CL pipeline notes that soon the node will no longer be available and it's aware of the existence of an alternative cobot node, robo-pi2. Finally, the cl-decision and cl-execution entities request the RO to migrate the cli-app to the replacement cobot, robo-pi2, as shown in the Node column.

These migration tests were performed multiple times. There were attempts to capture in a figure the application migration. This is, see how the application is terminated in one node and started in the other simultaneously. But this transition was too fast for us to capture. Therefore, the service doesn't exhibit any noticeable downtime.

As discussed in the following section, these tests establish the groundwork for the scenario described in Section III. In these tests, neither of the cobots were performing a surveillance mission, but were in a fixed position within close quarters. Nonetheless, the capabilities of a CL system are showcased with a satisfactory outcome.

VI. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper introduces an innovative framework for deploying cobot applications with the support of 6G networks. In alignment with the ZSM paradigm, CL systems are crucial for the development of Intent-based networks. The paper presents the implementation of a CL system capable of monitoring and operating a surveillance cobot cluster with a heightened level of autonomy.

At the time of the presentation of this paper, a demo is planned where the scenario presented in Section III will be implemented. Future work will consist on increasing the integration of this platform with the CL workflow, by adding more sensors to the robots, feeding more parameters into the CL system, and implementing the surveillance mission task and data processing pipeline.

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